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Risk of Ukraine's human capital loss and the means of its warning

*Valentyna Molokanova*¹, and *Ella Sergienko*²

¹ Dnipropetrovs'k Regional Institute for Public Administration, National Academy for Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, Management and Project Management Department, Gogol str., 29, 49044 Dnipro, Ukraine

² Dnipropetrovs'k Regional Institute for Public Administration, National Academy for Public Administration under the President of Ukraine, Management and Project Management Department, Gogol str., 29, 49044 Dnipro, Ukraine

Abstract. The impact of emigration processes in Ukraine on the decline of human capital potential is indicative as a set of unfavourable domestic conditions that are pushing the population out of their home country. In today's environment, the role of the individual as a special resource for economic development is increasing. Analysis of real processes of economy and society development in modern conditions has led to the establishment of human capital as the main productive and social factor. The preservation and development of human capital is a prerequisite for the effective growth of the national economy. The article examines statistics on labour migration in Ukraine, identifies the positive and negative consequences of labour migration. Special attention is paid to intellectual migrants as a major human capital resource. The results present as the spectrum of motivational values changes in different segments of the population. The main result of the study is a deepening of the theoretical framework for managing the risk of human capital loss. Recommendations for the careful regulation of intellectual migration have provided to stimulate the development of the national economy, improve the quality of human capital and increase the income level of the population.

1 Introduction

The preservation and development of human capital is a prerequisite for the effective functioning and growth of the national economy. The emergence of human capital theory is driven by the need for economic science to respond to changes in real life. With the advent of information value-oriented economy, there was a need for an in-depth understanding of the human role and the accumulated results of its intellectual activity on the pace and quality of economic development. The impetus for the creation of the theory of human capital was the growth statistics of the developed countries economies, which exceeded the calculations based on classical factors of growth. In a behavioural economy, the analysis of real processes has led to the affirmation of human capital as a major productive factor in the society development.

The role of psychological and socio-cultural factors in the economy in recent years has ceased to be underestimated, as it has been for decades before. Scientists have recognized that the processes of rapid change are increasingly dependent on the competencies of the individual who have to make decisions in today's challenging environment. The dominant

20 November 2020

characteristic of the human side of management is the ability to collaborate in a team and project environment [1]. The success of any project depends, primarily, on teamwork, and its quality depends largely on the personality of each team member [2]. Thus, the methodology of governance is becoming increasingly human-centred, as the cause and the main factor in the productive development of modern society. This opens a wide field of study of a human's personality: his views, values, motivations, reactions to life events that are, deeply individual factors.

In the second half of the twentieth century, the more common are the views of non-classical science, the object of which is the system, which depends of human behaviour. In this case, the subject of management and the system of its values become the focus of researchers. At the same time, management abandons rigid hierarchical management structures and moves to dynamic project-oriented systems, which are enshrined in new project management standards [3], [4]. Over time, the popularity of value-based management increases, which determines and structures the value-oriented approach to decision-making [5]. Continuing to study the particular culture of organizations is to investigate their mental space, as well as to develop a formalized description of such a space that allows influencing on the mental space of a project or program for the success of their implementation [6].

2 Data and Methods

Today, in the context of the modernization of the Ukrainian economy, there is a need to rethink basic theories and formulate modern concepts of human capital growth. The purpose of the article is to systematize theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of the human capital nature in the field of knowledge economy, to develop methodological bases for the study of its motivation and to characterize the impact on the economic growth of the country. The complexity of human capital management tasks requires a combination of technical, behavioural and contextual competencies, which determines the relevance of specific practices and managerial skills. However, the transition from an economic assessment of management effectiveness to an assessment of the effectiveness of human resource management processes is quite difficult. Currently, a methodology is needed that allows you to determine which percentage in creating a useful result belongs to effective human capital management, and which to other subject areas of modern management. To solve the tasks in this work, we used the method of critical analysis of scientific and statistical sources, methods of system analysis, generalization and systematization of practical experience.

3 Presentation of the main results

3.1. The category, nature and evolution of the concept of human capital

In our time of rapid social change, human capital is becoming a major factor in the formation and development of an innovative knowledge economy, as the next highest stage of development [7].

The current global trends in economic dynamics stimulate innovative development, which implies that human capital is a major factor in modernization. The implementation of technological advances in production depends more on human capital, which is an important component of the national wealth of any country. Therefore, today, human capital and its carrier recognized as one of the strategic resources in the developed countries of the world.

The term "human capital" is a broad interpretation of such concepts as human factor, human potential, and intellectual capital. Traditionally, the conceptual-categorical apparatus

20 November 2020

used to study human development and human capital operates with such terms as labor, human capital, human potential, labor potential, and social capital. These concepts can be considered as the main related categories used with the human capital category. Today, the normative acts and statistical records of most countries use the concept of "able-bodied population" of a country, an administrative territorial unit or an economic entity.

Labor potential is the ability to use labor resources in the long run. There are opportunities and skills of employees that today may not be used by the company, but in the future may be involved in social production. To characterize human capital, let us remember that capital is wealth, that is, accumulation. There are physical capital, natural capital, intellectual capital, depending on economic entities (person, enterprise, society), knowledge, skills, and natural abilities.

3.2. Statistical indicators of labour migration in Ukraine

The main issue of migration, which is much more written by media and politicians, is the external labour migration of Ukrainians, which has a serious impact on the economic development of the whole country. The State Statistics Service considers migrant workers as persons aged 15-70 who have worked or sought work abroad for less than one year. Estimates that the scale of labour migration obtained from a number of sociological surveys are higher due to the lack of methodological constraints in determining the contingent of external labour migrants. In one of the polls of the end of 2018, mass travel of Ukrainian citizens abroad was named as one of the main threats to the country by 59% of respondents [8].

In Ukraine, they are now talking about the "fifth wave" of emigration, which continues the large-scale migration processes of the 20th and early 21st centuries [9]. There are millions of people involved in labour migration. In 2018, according to the National Bank of Ukraine, the volume of private transfers from abroad has grown to \$ 11.6 billion, which is significantly higher than FDI, and is forecast to reach 12.2 billion by the end of 2019 [10]. In its latest report on Ukraine, the International Monetary Fund called labour migration one of the reasons for rising wages (due to competition with foreign employers, Ukraine is forced to raise wages).

Table 1. Results of the survey by the State Statistics Service of Ukraine on labour migrants [10]

Years	Number, million	% of working age population of Ukraine
2005-2006	1,5 million	5,1
2010-2012	1,2 million	3,4
2015-2018	1,3 million	4,5

Among the reasons for labour migration is the low level of wages. The number of jobs in Ukraine is increasing, but labor migration is not decreasing. Thus, according to the State Employment Service in the Lviv region over the last two years, the number of vacancies has increased by 50%. Among the 8,000 vacancies, 2/3 are the workforce, 1/3 are specialists with higher education. The state employment service in the labor market fills a niche of about 26 percent of the total number of employees [10]. That means, there is a real need for staff, employers are experiencing a frantic staffing hunger.

At present, the topic of migration in Ukraine has traditionally been at the forefront of political, informational and economic media. This phenomenon has also become the object of populist manipulation and misinterpretation. Particularly acute is its coverage every year

20 November 2020

in the summer, when in high school begins an entrance exams and there is a noticeable migration loss of youth potential. Against the background of the protracted demographic crisis, the migrant sentiment of the students not only blocks the processes of preserving the resource potential of the national educational and scientific schools, but also leads to the destruction of the socio-cultural foundations of the domestic labour market, producing threats to the national security of the country.

Table 2. Number of labor migrants by occupational groups [10]

	Total, thousand people	Total,%
Total number of migrant workers who worked before departure abroad by occupational groups:	736,3	
– professionals, specialists, technical employees	161,7	8,2
– trade and service workers	126,2	11,2
– skilled workers in agriculture, forestry, fisheries and fisheries	11,4	1,7
– skilled workers with the tool	218,4	32,1
– maintenance and control workers for technological equipment and machinery	74,4	7,2
– the simplest professions	144,2	39,6

3.3. The theory and technologies of human capital conservation

In the world, the critical mass of labour migration for the country is 12%. That is, labour migration in Ukraine is not as acute as it may seem. Smart businesses can identify potential migrant workers among their employees, direct them to their own subsidiaries abroad and receive more qualified staff, but for some reason they don't. Obviously, such Enterprises, which for some reason do not do so, will have problems with labour in other countries.

A recent study on migration highlights defined several key reasons for people leaving the country. In the first place, among the causes of labour migration is low wages. According to the study first group of migrants are people who travel abroad for a short period to earn targeted funds. The second group of migrant workers includes those who seek to change the picture of life. This group is also numerous. In the third group, there are people who want to travel. They are mostly young people. For them, making money abroad is an opportunity to see the world, get to know other cultures and traditions. Increasingly, scholars are finding that earning migration which taking new forms and goals. Undoubtedly, each of us has the right to choose the conditions of our lives and work. However, today we are talking about those risks to the state of the loss of human capital.

Especially dangerous is the modern fifth wave of migration, which dates back to the second decade of the 20th century and is essentially educational. Today, young people go abroad in different ways. Someone to get better pay, someone better education, the opportunity to better communicate with similar ones through learning a different language. According to a study by Lviv Polytechnic National University, over 90 percent of students studying construction and architecture, IT, chemistry, etc., declare that they want to go abroad in order to arrange their lives there. Therefore, the Ukrainian government needs to take immediate steps to ensure that Ukrainian students remain in Ukraine. It is necessary to create such a package of social services that would keep the teacher and the student in Ukraine. Another task is the realization of the strategic planning for the development of the

20 November 2020

territory of Ukraine, the development of a program of revival of certain sectors of the economy, which would determine the economic face of a region.

To date, labour migration not only reduces the supply of labour in the Ukrainian labour market, but also reduces its quality. Intellectual migration is a particular threat to the socio-economic development of the country and the sustainable development of society. Unfortunately, today more than 30% of Ukrainian scientists are working on the development of the economy of foreign countries [11]. The migration policy of many developed countries of the world is based on the principle of attracting an intellectual migrant [12]. In a globalized world, it is impossible to stop intellectual migration, which can have both positive and negative consequences for the country (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Positive and negative consequences of emigration [13]

Intellectual migration is a rather urgent problem for modern Ukraine, and it needs to introduce a mechanism for returning migrants to their homeland, that is, a mechanism for the transformation of irreversible emigration into a temporary one.

In order to reduce the scope of intellectual migration, the state should focus its policy on the development and effective using of intellectual potential:

- to provide decent wages to the scientific potential of the country;
- ensure the updating of the material and technical base of the research sphere;
- to provide new approaches to the realization of the formation of human resources potential by determining the priority areas for the state in which the training of scientific personnel should be carried out;
 - create favourable working conditions, with laboratories equipped with the necessary technical facilities, which will facilitate the realization of creative and intellectual potential;
 - to increase the level of social protection of scientific workers;
 - to stimulate domestic business to the effective using of scientific developments of Ukrainian scientists;
 - to promote international cooperation with the opportunity to travel abroad.

Thereby, in the age of globalization, migration policy becomes a factor of state innovative development. Migration is increasingly affecting the quality of human capital, and the income level of the population. Countries are faced with the challenge of attracting the most effective part of human capital from abroad, the preservation and development of

20 November 2020

national intellectual resources and technology transfer through specialists. These goals require developing a security strategy to save state human capital.

4 Conclusion

Loss of intellectual capital of the country is a complex phenomenon that has an ambiguous impact on socio-economic development. Today, in the international labour market, Ukraine holds one of the leading positions among the donor countries in intellectual resources and actually participates in the economically developed countries of the world.

The current crisis of national science is the main cause of intellectual migration, which negatively affects at the development of the national economy, the quality of human capital, labour productivity, and the income level of the population.

The official statistical sources are unable to estimate the real scale of intellectual migration, due to the lack of unified methodological approaches to measuring the intensity of migration processes of highly skilled workers. This has a negative impact on the ability to evaluate the quantitative and qualitative parameters of intellectual work. Therefore, the first important step in public policy to improve the information level of statistical indicators is to introduce the most advanced processing technology. It is also necessary to improve the survey of migration processes.

Accordingly, Ukraine has just begun to form a comprehensive, scientifically substantiated methodical, information-weighted system for regulating intellectual migration processes. Implementation of attentive and careful regulation of intellectual migration in combination with market processes of self-regulation is able to stabilize the situation regarding intellectual migration, stimulate the development of the national economy, improve the quality of human capital, and increase the level of income of the population.

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20 November 2020

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